
Series: PHYSICS

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Electric charge of a photon

Annotation

The mechanism of propagation of an electromagnetic wave in a direct current wire is considered. It is assumed that the same mechanism is implemented for the propagation of an electromagnetic wave in a vacuum. This assumption allows us to find the electric charge of the photon.

In [1], the existence of electromagnetic induction is substantiated (theoretically and experimentally), which differs from Faraday's electromagnetic induction and is called the fourth electromagnetic induction. It can arise, in particular, as a result of the action of a parallel wire, the current of which creates in this wire a magnetic strength with a vector perpendicular to the axis of this wire. In this case, a longitudinal flow of electromagnetic energy is created in this wire. This flow creates a fourth electromagnetic induction, which manifests itself as a force acting on the wire's electrons. This force creates a current in the secondary circuit. Finally, this current creates strengths, the consequence of which is again the appearance of a flow of electromagnetic energy, and so on. This is how an electromagnetic wave propagates along an electrically conductive wire.

For what follows, it is important for us to note that the **flow of electromagnetic energy creates a force acting on the electrons of the wire**. The movement of electrons creates strengths, which again result in the appearance of a flow of electromagnetic energy, and so on.

The propagation of an electromagnetic wave in a vacuum can be represented in exactly the same way, if we assume that photons are electric charges. We accept this assumption, since no other mechanism of wave motion has been proposed, and the neutrality of the photon is still questioned – see, for example, [2].

Next, a method for calculating the value of the photon charge is proposed. It was shown in [1] that at a constant value of the electromagnetic energy flux in the wire, this flux creates a force with a density

$$e = \frac{1}{\gamma} \frac{S\sqrt{\epsilon\mu}}{c}, \quad (1)$$

where γ is a coefficient that has the dimension of electric charge density. Thus, the flow of electromagnetic energy acts on an electric charge with force (6). This force is called the fourth emf and is the electrical strength.

It was shown in [3], as a consequence of solving the Mumswell equations for an electromagnetic wave in vacuum, that a radial electric field with amplitude e creates in a cylindrical wave an energy flux with a density

$$S = \frac{c}{2} \sqrt{\frac{\epsilon}{\mu}} e^2. \quad (2)$$

Combining (1) and (2), we get:

$$S = \frac{c}{2} \sqrt{\frac{\epsilon}{\mu}} e^2 = \frac{c}{2} \sqrt{\frac{\epsilon}{\mu}} \left(\frac{1}{\gamma} \frac{S\sqrt{\epsilon\mu}}{c} \right)^2 = \frac{1}{2c} \sqrt{\frac{\epsilon}{\mu}} \epsilon\mu \left(\frac{S}{\gamma} \right)^2 \quad (3)$$

or

$$1 = \frac{1}{2c} \sqrt{\frac{\epsilon}{\mu}} \epsilon\mu S \gamma^{-2} \quad (4)$$

or

$$\gamma = \sqrt{\frac{S}{2c}} \epsilon^{3/4} \mu^{1/4}. \quad (5)$$

The energy density of a photon in its volume V is equal to

$$w = \frac{\hbar\omega}{V}. \quad (6)$$

It is known that

$$\frac{S}{w} = c. \quad (7)$$

From (6, 7) we get:

$$S = \frac{\hbar\omega c}{V}. \quad (8)$$

From (5, 8) we get:

$$\gamma = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar\omega c}{V} \frac{1}{2c}} \epsilon^{3/4} \mu^{1/4} = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar\omega}{2V}} \epsilon^{3/4} \mu^{1/4} \quad (9)$$

The value of γ can be represented as

$$\gamma = \frac{q}{V} \quad (10)$$

where q is the photon charge. Then

$$q = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar\omega V}{2}} \epsilon^{3/4} \mu^{1/4}. \quad (11)$$

It was shown in [4] that a photon has the shape of a cube with an edge

$$L = \sqrt[3]{\frac{3}{\mu\epsilon}} 2\pi/\omega. \quad (12)$$

Therefore, the volume of a photon

$$V = 8\pi^3 \left(\frac{3}{\mu\varepsilon}\right)^{1.5} / \omega^3. \quad (13)$$

Next, from (11, 13) we find

$$\begin{aligned} q &= \sqrt{\frac{\hbar\omega}{2}} \varepsilon^{3/4} \mu^{1/4} \left(8\pi^3 \left(\frac{3}{\mu\varepsilon}\right)^{1.5} / \omega^3\right)^{1/2} = \\ &= (8\pi^3)^{1/2} \sqrt{\frac{\hbar\omega\omega^{-3}}{2}} \varepsilon^{3/4} \mu^{1/4} \left(\frac{3}{\mu\varepsilon}\right)^{3/4} \end{aligned}$$

or

$$q = \frac{\vartheta}{\omega^2} \sqrt{\hbar}, \quad (14)$$

where

$$\vartheta = \left(2 \cdot 3^{3/4} \pi^{3/2} \sqrt{\frac{1}{\mu}}\right). \quad (15)$$

Thus, a **photon has an electrical charge that depends on the frequency.**

References

1. S.I. Khmelnik. Fourth Electromagnetic Induction. The Papers of Independent Authors, ISSN 2225-6717, 2022, 55, 19–26. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5887980>
2. Brett Altschul. Bound on the Photon Charge from the Phase Coherence of Extragalactic Radiation // *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 98, 261801 (2007), arXiv: hep-ph/0703126.
3. S.I. Khmelnik. Inconsistency Solution of Maxwell's Equations (Chapter 1). 19th edition, pp. 1-378, 2020, ISBN 978-1-365-23941-0. Printed in USA, Lulu Inc., ID 19043222, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5796226>
4. S.I. Khmelnik. Photon structure. The Papers of Independent Authors, ISSN 2225-6717, 2021, 55, 13–18. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5733304>